

GENERAL DESCRIPTION OF DENTAL PROSTHESIS AND THEIR TYPES

Ismailov Bahadirjon Uraimovich

Assistant of the Department of Orthopedic Dentistry and Orthodontics,
Faculty of Dentistry, Andijan State Medical Institute.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10824452>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 08th March 2024

Accepted: 15th March 2024

Online: 16th March 2024

KEYWORDS

*Prosthesis, dental procedures,
single crown, bridge prosthesis,
artificial structures,
diction, cosmetic defect.*

ABSTRACT

This article is a general classification of dentures, their types it was written about positive and negative evaluation, as well as removable teeth.

Prosthodontics is the branch of dentistry that deals with the design, manufacture and fitting of artificial teeth and mouth substitutes. It is a branch of dentistry that focuses on the aesthetics and function of human dentition.

The science of creating natural-looking teeth within a smile is called prosthetics and prosthodontics. It includes bridges, crowns, bridges, teeth, and implant-retained restorations.

Some of these surgeries are permanent in your mouth, while others are removable. Before recommending surgery, your dentist will consider factors such as the number of missing teeth, the condition of your existing teeth, and the thickness of your jawbone to determine whether removable dentures or fixed prosthodontics are a better fit for that particular tooth situation.

Prosthetic dentistry operations are necessary when hard tooth tissue is lost due to dental caries, overly hermetic seals, or damage caused by tooth wear. Prosthetic dentistry is also indicated after endodontic dental therapy, as the loss of tooth vitality increases the likelihood of tooth fracture. By connecting the prosthesis with a dental implant, it is possible to restore an entire tooth crown in case of tooth loss.

Modern dentistry works great. However, old age teeth are not very easy to maintain. In any case, prostheses are needed. Meanwhile there is a wide range of products. But, nevertheless, many they don't know which dental procedures are best. Opinions of dentists, the uniqueness and, of course, the disadvantages of any particular product shows that there is. All this is in the process of selecting the material should be taken into account. Issues of compensation for teeth defects in the modern world does not lose their importance. Unfortunately, harmful production, unstable environmental situation, unsatisfactory food composition, food quality, etc factors, as before, have a parallel effect on the health of the teeth with the hereditary factor shows.

Fortunately, only one question needs to be asked today – what prosthetic protections are acceptable in a particular situation. Let's see why it is important to understand the types of prostheses. Modern people do not worry - in the field of dentistry news can solve any problem and even in the most difficult situations can restore the integrity of the teeth. Of course, many people are even the best that he does not want to install dentures and at the same time chew his front teeth they say. But what happens to their dental system do they report on themselves?

Do not think that you need to restore a missing tooth. After all, sooner or later the compensation mechanism reaches its limits and teeth are lost leads to the following violation: cosmetic defect; Difficulty with diction; problems with chewing food; violation of the bite and, as a result, in the work of the temporomandibular joint violation;

Development or exacerbation of periodontal disease symptoms; the appearance of increased enamel displacement; arches of a row of permanent teeth; the appearance of wedge-shaped defects.

What are the types of dentures?

All types of dentures in removable and non-removable parts is divided. Acceptable prostheses are often featured in movies and comics "grandmother's" dentures. Indeed, such prosthetics and reality often used in the elderly, it is a lot of tooth loss from caries and its complications, periodontitis. However, there is nothing to laugh about, because removable dentures millions of people are complete in terms of nutrition and both communication and aesthetics helps them come back to life. The feature of this prosthesis is the prosthesis is the need for daily hygiene. Acceptable dentures can be complete, that is, teeth in the mouth defects that are completely missing, and partially - significant, but complete teeth are covered by the loss.

Traditionally, a support for removable prostheses the material is acrylic plastic. More about removable dentures modern types are nylon prostheses. Special for their production aesthetic nylon is used, which has the best aesthetic properties, durable provides strength and long-term use. Fixed prostheses teeth clarity, discoloration or tooth used to change small defects in the shape. This includes the following includes:

Crowns. They are made of metal, ceramic (ceramic coated metal made of alloy), ceramics, plastics.

Bridges. Construction of several crowns, the end of which is connected to the vertical teeth and covers the middle (1-3 pieces) existing defect.

Shortcuts. Microwaves are often made of ceramic materials poplars, instead of restoring the shape and color of these teeth, teeth and its complications instead of filling with

Veneers. Qualitative elimination of cosmetic defects in front teeth thin porcelain or ceramic plates.

Depending on the location of the prosthesis, there are two types of maxillofacial prosthesis:

Intraoral prostheses: prostheses include soft and hard palates, assistive speech devices, oral exercises, and swallowing aids.

Extraoral prostheses: includes orbital implants, as well as ocular, nasal, ear, and cranial prostheses.

Some of the advantages of maxillofacial prosthesis are as follows:

Restoration of organ structure and functions

Cosmetic benefits

Rebuilding self-confidence

Improving the patient's quality of life

After prosthetic surgery, it is very important to maintain the proper hygienic care of dentures and to follow the recommendations of the dentist in order to prolong the life of the prosthesis. Sometimes the prosthesis can be dislocated; Therefore, regular research is strongly encouraged.

Implant prosthodontics

A dental implant is an artificial tooth root. Its purpose is to anchor smooth teeth to the jawbone.

Dental implants look like screws, jawbones look like a piece of wood. In this scenario, half of the screw's length would be driven into the wood, and an artificial tooth would be attached to the part of the screw that protrudes from the wood.

The screw is firmly fixed to the wood, and the tooth is firmly attached to the screw. A single dental implant can replace a single missing tooth. 4-8 dental implants can be placed in a missing jaw.

Dental implants must be placed in sufficient bone that is free of infection. Sometimes surgery is necessary to clean out an existing infection or to build more bone for implant procedures such as bone ridge augmentation or nasal sinus lift. The procedure for placing dental implants is the same as for tooth extraction.

After implantology therapy, many types of prostheses are used, which include:

A crown based on a single implant: the largest option for replacing a single tooth element. It is the most basic operation in the field of implantology. The crown, that is, the component that takes the shape of the tooth, is attached to the implant with a screw.

Implant Supported Bridge: This is a fixed bridge technique. To provide just one example, three teeth can be replaced by two implants. When a specialist uses this procedure to rehabilitate the entire mouth, it is called implant-supported comprehensive rehabilitation.

Implantation preserves overcrowding: using 2-4 implants, the removable denture increases, which further corrects the denture even if it can be removed.

Instant download. In some cases, and always after a good study, a temporary fixed prosthesis based on implants can be made on the same day of their installation. This approach allows patients to be edentulous during the implant integration phase and eliminates the need for a temporary removable prosthesis. However, this therapy is not suitable for many patients.

Advantages of prosthetic dentistry dentures are used to correct defects such as missing or missing teeth. Replacements, implants, cosmetic dentistry, and restorations are some of the methods used to treat oral tissue disorders.

The increasing prevalence of periodontal disorders across all age groups is creating a huge demand for dental prostheses.

Apart from oral diseases, more comprehensive income, realization that dentures are the best therapy for tooth replacement and restoration, expansion of medical tourism are all the reasons for the growing market.

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